
FEMINISM AND EDUCATION

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Abstract

Education is a tool that embosses hidden inside in men. Men grow as age, time and circumstances and education is an integral part in human life that is omnipotent in all ages, for all types of groups not only for human even for animal world. Education sharpens wit, teaches to apply logic to sustain in the globe and to develop it. Its limitation is limitless so different perspectives of human lives are filling ocean of education as drops. It has been contributing society with a vision to look at macro level never comes to an end. People of all types, all age groups, literate, illiterate, outdated, modern and of different professions and occupations have been contributing to niche this corner. Among them writers community undoubtedly paying to society in general to evolve and spread. And among them flag warriors who are supports of self-reliant women, have been germinating a sense of responsibility in community. Taking care of the point feminists writer's contribution to education industry already done and can be done, is highlighted in the paper.

Keywords: Feminists, psychology, case study, Avid Reading, Children Literature, Law.

Feminists believe society is male dominated –in other words it is a patriarchy. Feminists also believe that society is based on conflict between the sexes. They believe that women have historically been disadvantaged in society and that men historically have had more power than women. Feminists believe this is wrong and needs changing. There are many different feminist theories but they all share things in common – they look at the differences in society between men and women and try to see how these problems could be solved. Feminists believe that education is an agent of secondary socialization that helps to enforce patriarchy. They look at society on a MACRO scale. They want to generalize their ideas about males and females to the whole of society.

Feminism has many types and principles. Liberal feminists writing about education use concepts of equal opportunities, socialization, sex roles and discrimination. Their strategies involve altering socialization practices, changing attitudes and making use of relevant legislation. Socialist feminists analyze the role of the school in the perpetuation of gender divisions under capitalism. Major concepts are socio-cultural reproduction and to a lesser extent acceptance of and resistance to gender-based patterns of behaviour. Radical feminists in education have concentrated mainly on the male monopolization of knowledge and culture and on sexual politics in schools. Strategies involve putting women's and girls' concerns first, through separate-sex groups when necessary. All the theoretical frameworks are subject to the same pressures including the oppressive power of structures, the resilience of individuals, and the tension between universality (how women are the same) and diversity (how women differ on attributes like class and race).

College and School Studies:

Fact should be taken in note that if a woman is educated, she can educate whole family. Family is the first brick of the society and society is foundation of nation. It's a universal doctrine. Feminism movements have established many an elite colleges that had been resulted for the first time in the history of higher education for women has challenged male hegemony over the curriculum and over knowledge itself through 'Women-Curriculum.' Schools are opened for higher education in special reference to support

girls' education to demean prevalent social evil customs which have been treating women as an object of fulfillment.

Deeper Learning:

Feminism is a vast subject having many kinds of themes as so rich in its different types. In school and colleges, students can be given topics for 'Group Discussion' and for 'Debate' topics such as "Feminism is subjugating men" or "Increasing rate of literacy in women is cause of increasing rate in divorces." In colleges in Literature subjects, Communication Skills and in Human Resources types of subject can cater such topics as assignments also to judge oral, written, logical and critical power of students in fair and innovative ways. This processor paves path of "Deeper Learning"

"Through the process of deeper learning, students develop 21st century competencies—which encompass both knowledge and skills—that can be transferred to new situations or problems within a subject or field. In contrast to a view of 21st century skills as general skills that can be applied to a range of different tasks in various R 4 Education for Life and Work: Guide for Practitioners civic, workplace, or family contexts, research so far suggests that these competencies are specific to—and intertwined with—knowledge of a particular discipline or subject area" (NRC 3-4)

Case Studies:

Feminism study provides ample of opportunities of learning. Writers pay great attention towards She-Sex to make them part of common line people. The world is full of bitter facts of violence, rape, physical, mental, emotional abuse on the ground of gender discrimination. It's shocking to know that precursor of western culture-Britain has almost highest number of domestic violence cases against women. It's really tough to imagine about backward areas as many heinous cases pops up as headline on media of women's suffering and Hellenic life. Simon de Beauvoir, Alice Walker, Sylvia Plath, Kate Millet, Naomi Wolf, Gayatri Sivpak, Nayan Tara Sehgal, Bharti Mukherjee, Chitra Divakaruni Banerjee, Monica Ali, Kiran Desai, Jhumpa Lahiri are well known names around the globe who have advocated women's rights in their novels so boldly.

Bharti Mukherjee's most famous character Jasmine, Chitra's ultimate voice through Draupadi, Nazneen of Monica Ali, Alice Walker's Nettie, Desai's Bela and endless protagonists along with minor and supporting female characters make their own world to learn and to teach. It's a genuine thought to take these female characters in 'Role Play' group discussion for qualitative summative progress in learning process away from stereotyped established syllabus. Y- generation and adult's opinion matter a lot in the development of community cultural structure. They are torch bearers, future of the country so they can excel the country and globe to another level of advancement if society becomes liberal and logical in thoughts. Present generation can play major role to enhance the idea of respective treatment towards this gender and a practical concept of cohesive world to establish peaceful territory. Malala Yusufzai is a live example of women education and feminism for a big change in the world.

"When someone tells me about Malala, the girl who was shot by the Taliban – that's my definition for her – I don't think she's me. Now I don't even feel as if I was shot. Even my life in Swat feels like a part of history or a movie I watched. Things change. God has given us a brain and a heart which tell us how to live" (Lane, The Guardian).

Avid Reading in special reference to Feminism and Careers:

There is a stream found of avid readers in all age groups all over the world and genuinely they are found good and excellent observers of incidences, characters and phenomenas. Later on, these minds and brains flourish knowledge and provide benefits being as psychiatrists, psychological counselors in

academic and co-operate groups, psycho-medico consultants for mental physical ailments, spiritual healers etc. 'Wife' of Bharti Mukherjee is such a precise presentation of neurotic disorder of Dimple Dasgupta, which can be utilized for psychiatrists for case study in a very effective way.

“A case study is a research approach that is used to generate an in-depth multi-faceted understanding of a complex issue in its real-life context. It is an established research design that is used extensively in a wide variety of disciplines, particularly in the social sciences” (Sheikh).

Feminist's writers have written a lot about children also to project human behavior's multi aspects. Feminism support children Literature strongly, which is a fundamental need for all round development. This point can be well understood by this fact only that increasing bad temperament and criminal attitude among children has showcased lack of proper environment in their nourishment as society has gone far apart from natural human tendencies because of fast growth of so called world. In these cat races, innocents minds are not shaped that's a reason that even media and film industries are also having lack of good content, teaching and values for children. It's resonating with schools and families as well on same path.

Moreover basic traits for mind development come out from the development of four skills: Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing. Feminists' writers have spoken boldly and tried their best to open eyes of people from stereotyped thinking. In the similar way, many such novels and narration collection have been contributing to the field of 'Law' to solve complicated cases after understanding all the facts of cases. This is coined as 'Feminist Legal Theory.'

“Feminist legal theory or feminist jurisprudence is based on the belief that the law has been fundamental in women's historical subordination. The project of feminist legal theory is twofold. First, feminist jurisprudence seeks to explain ways in which the law played a role in women's former subordinate status. Second, feminist legal theory is dedicated to changing women's status through a rework of the law and its approach to gender” (Aslam).

Conclusion:

Feminism and feminists have paid tremendous roles all the way in the growth whether its global or national development or peace- making or education or safety security of women from domestic violence or from tiring cruel net of social ills against them prevalent since centuries. It has given a respectable position and advocacy power to the world to understand difference between right and wrong. Moreover it is not left as movement to support a particular motif but has expanded to do welfare all the way out. Finally, feminism envisions a peaceful future that take into consideration women, other marginalized people, and gender. A number of themes continue to emerge from feminist engagement such as forgiveness, reconciliation, and transitional justice –themes situated at the intersection of peace/violence and religion.

A feminist perspective based on the experiences of women can add new dimensions to understand the world politics system. Feminists' international relations scholars seek to illuminate how the International Relations are a gender construction, in which both men and women are essential actors in the real world.

"A feminist is anyone who recognizes the equality and full humanity of women and men" (Steneim).

Feminism has out sourced an insight of equal opportunity, humanity and a peaceful world full of love,

understanding and logical life for all kinds of people. Feminism doesn't restrict itself into the walls of women but the whole world is sitting in its lap to have a beautiful nap.

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